

DEVELOPMENT OF SPEAKING COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS THROUGH STUDYING PAHLAVAN MAHMUD'S RUBAI

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ABSTRACT: This scientific article reflects on the methods of forming the elements of speech competence through an innovative approach in teaching the students of the academic lyceum the grace of Pahlavon Mahmud rubai, the skill of choosing words, the use of artistic image tools, and the methods of creating skills. It is shown that the tools of artistic imagery in lyrics, the masterpieces of poetic art, reveal their inner, hidden abilities of students and encourage them to think creatively and come up with promising ideas.

KEY WORDS: competence, «Autofocus method», lojuvard, drunk, foolish , zeru dast, zunnor, target.

Each lesson topic covers different methods based on its purpose. These methods lead to the effectiveness of the lesson, students fully mastering the subject and applying it in their own life. The success of the learning process depends on the teacher and the student. If there is a specialist with excellent experience, but the process is irrelevant or uninteresting for the learner, high efficiency cannot be achieved. Or, on the contrary, if the student has a high interest in the lesson, subject, and subject, but if the teacher is not knowledgeable in his subject, a skilled pedagogue, if he does not have love for his profession and children, the intended result cannot be achieved.

One of the primary causes of a dull learning environment in the classroom is poor attention, apathy, and laziness among students. In such a situation, the main responsibility falls on the teacher. In any case, students should be able to focus on

the lesson. Depending on the course of the lesson, the psychological state of the students, the level of knowledge, the level of understanding of the lesson, he should be able to choose a suitable method. For this, first of all, strong knowledge, skills and creativity are required. One of the methods used in such a situation is the «Autofocus method». Through this method, it is possible to easily solve the problems of students in mastering the lesson. It ensures that students pay attention to the optional lesson.

Red and white cards are required when using the Autofocus method. These cards are distributed to each student in the class. This is done at the beginning of the lesson. Then suddenly a question is asked during the lesson. Let's say the questions are as follows: «Let those with red cards stand up». And an optional question on the topic will be given to any one of the students. If they find the answer, one point is added to the red card group. No points will be awarded if they fail to answer or answer incorrectly.

Then, during the lesson, it is suddenly called, «Let those with white cards stand up» and, as above, the students with white cards are asked a question about the topic. In this order, this method is used several times until the end of the lesson. As a result, all students will be alert during the lesson. Concentration of attention will also be in place. As a result, everyone fully participates in the lesson, the subject covered in the lesson, the reinforced points are well preserved in the student's memory. This method increases the signals of interest in the lesson in the process of getting students to move, i.e. get up. In addition, the questions asked to any student will force everyone to listen carefully to the topic. In this process, the competition will go away, and a healthy competitive environment will be created. Students focus on the subject of the lesson by competing with each other. That is, students will have an Autofocus environment. This method can be used in all subjects. It is especially effective in literature classes.

When teaching the subject of Pahlavon Mahmud's Rubaiyat to students of the academic lyceum, it is appropriate to use the «Autofocus method» in the following order. First, opinions are exchanged about Pahlavon Mahmud's life, work, and literary heritage, and students give information based on their knowledge. The teacher enriches ideas with theoretical information and fills in gaps. Then samples from the author's writings are analyzed. In the literary analysis, the teacher mainly points out the places that should be emphasized one by one. In the main part of the lesson, using the «Autofocus method», the groups are given the numbered rubai texts given to the students with white and red cards, and they are asked to analyze them. Points are awarded for correct answers. No marks will be deducted for an incorrect answer. Then it will be analyzed by Rubaiyats.

THE RUBIANS

1. There is courage - it is a work of enthusiasm,

Do not torture your wife

If the fruit branch overhangs the wall,

Passengers reach for him.

A truly brave and zealous man warns that he will not leave his wife in the street, saying that the consequences will not be good, and he expresses it with high artistic skill.

2. Black stone is an indescribable gem,

It is not contagious to a pure heart.

Listen to the words of Puryoyvali,

Is there any brave from the cowards?

In this Rubaiyat, it is emphasized that just as an ordinary black stone never shines like a precious stone and does not delight the eyes, so also cowards never become brave.

3. I said: tell me, what is the meaning of life?

He said: lightning, or a candle, or a propeller.

I said: who built this world?

He said: either empty, drunk, or crazy.

Pahlavon Mahmud compares the transience of life to a flash of lightning or a candle that burns out, and says that only a fool or a fool can love it.

4. Do not cut down the tree of our life, Lord,

Do not make me drunk with the wine of existence, Lord.

You are a brave young man

Don't look down on the mistakes, Lord.

O Lord, do not cut down the tree of our life, make us drunk with the wine of existence, and make your many brave young men like dots in the hands of the poor.

5. The face of the world is yours,

Mind is a river - you are its water.

Do not sit like dew on a flower leaf,

You are the color of this kindergarten.

You are the color of this world, you are the mind, the water of the river. Do not sit like dew on a flower leaf, you are the color of the flower garden.

6. O friend, tell me if you need a life, I will give my life

Whatever you ask, my dearest, I will give it to you

O infidel Shaddad, come to me,
I will take your prayer and believe instead.

O friend, tell me, if you need my life, I will give my life, ask for any of my dearest things, and I will give it. O infidel Shaddad, come to me, take your leather belt and give me my faith in its place.

7. Doubts and doubts in your heart are gone,
Spirit power is also gone for a day, believe me.
Don't brag about finding a clear target,
If you find it, your target is gone.

In this rubai, the writer used a beautiful play on words. Doubts and suspicions in your heart will disappear, believe me, the strength of your soul will also disappear one day, do not be proud that you have found a clear target, the target you have found may disappear.

8. A good friend is a true friend if he says he is right.
The one who prays is a true friend.
The eye never gave or received bread,
Bread is not a friend, in fact, a soul friend is a true friend.

A friend who smokes in the path of truth is a true friend, a friend who prays to the end is a true friend, don't show off the bread you give or take, in fact, it is not a bread friend, but a soul friend is a true friend.

So, it is worthwhile to follow the example of Pahlavon Mahmud's life and work. As highly spiritual, sharp observational works, his rubai's are gaining great importance in educating young people and developing their ideological consciousness. The "Autofocus method" in teaching literary works to students is important for keeping attention for a long time, not getting distracted, and quickly and easily mastering the subject.

List of used literature:

1. Literature. N. Sulaymanova and others. Textbook for academic lyceum 1st level. T:- 2023.
2. Law of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education". - T.: 2020. September 3-2.
3. Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-4910. – T.: December 3, 2020, Appendix 3, Clause 3
4. Decision No. 646 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the introduction of the national test system for assessing the level of knowledge of general education subjects". - T. : 2020. October 12.
5. Tokhliyev B., Karimov B., Usmanova K. Literature. textbook. 10th grade. Part 1. - T.: "National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan". 2017. Page 177